

Amberlite IR-120 catalyzed, microwave-assisted one-pot synthesis of amides from nitriles by Ritter reaction

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Abstract : A variety of alkenes and alcohols undergo one-pot amidation with nitriles in the presence of amberlite IR-120 as a mild and effective catalyst under microwave irradiation and mild conditions to afford the corresponding secondary amides in good to excellent yields. This is a highly efficient method for the preparation of α -arylethyl amides especially from alcohols and vinyl arenes without any side reactions such as olefin polymerization. The use of readily available and easy to handle reagent amberlite IR-120 makes this method simple, convenient, and practical.

Keywords : Ritter amidation, alcohols, alkenes, nitriles, amberlite IR-120, α -arylethyl amides.

Introduction

The search for new, simple and selective methods for the C–N bond formation remains a challenge for chemists. Among the classical approaches towards the amide functionality, the Ritter reaction appears as a general method for the amidation of alcohols or alkenes¹. The synthesis of α -arylethyl amides derivatives is currently of much interest, and various methods have been reported for their synthesis^{2,3}. However, these methods require high temperatures (100 °C and 150 °C, respectively), hence limiting the scope of the reaction. The development of an environmentally benign methodology for the synthesis of pyrazolones derivatives is of great interest.

Therefore, the discovery of clean procedures and the use of green and eco-friendly catalysts with high catalytic activity and short reaction times for the production of amidation's of olefins and alcohols have gained considerable attention.

Results and discussion

In continuation with the search for simple non-hazardous methods for the transformations in organic synthesis⁴⁻⁸, we report here the use of amberlite IR-120 [H⁺]

resin as a highly efficient and homogeneous organic catalyst for the exclusive synthesis of α -arylethyl amides (**3**) from condensation of vinyl arenes (**1**) and alcohols (**2**) with nitriles under microwave irradiation.

Initially, we attempted the coupling of styrene (**1**) with acetonitrile as a model reaction using catalytic amounts of amberlite IR-120 under microwave irradiation (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

For optimizing the reaction, firstly, styrene (1 mmol) and acetonitrile (1 mmol) were taken, and 0.16 g of amberlite IR-120 was added and the mixture was carried out under the influence of microwave irradiation, the reaction proceeded effectively affording the product in 91% yield in 8 min. After optimizing these conditions, the reactions were performed with various vinyl arenes and other nitrile derivatives. The results of this study are pre-

sented in Table 1. It is noteworthy, no reaction was observed in the absence of amberlite IR-120 even after an extended reaction time (12 min).

The activation of alcohols to generate the carbocation is thought to be difficult due to the poor leaving ability of

Table-1 (contd.)

Table 1. Ritter reaction of various vinyl arenes and nitriles catalyzed by amberlite IR-120 under microwave irradiation

Entry	Olefin (1)	Nitrile (2)	Product ^a (3)	Time (min)	Yields ^b (%)
1		CH ₃ CN		8	91
2		CH ₃ CN		7	89
3		CH ₃ CN		8	90
4		CH ₃ CN		6	93
5		CH ₃ CN		8	88
6		CH ₃ CN		7	95
7		CH ₃ CN		9	90
8		CH ₃ CN		6	89
9		CH ₃ CN		6	91
10				9	90
11				8	88

12				9	90
13				8	91
14				9	90

(a) Isolated yields. (b) All the products are known, characterized by IR, NMR spectral analysis and compared with the authentic samples⁹⁻¹¹. (c) Melting points of compounds are consistent with reported values.

the -OH group in the absence of any catalyst. In continuation the present study, alcohols were used with a variety of aromatic/aliphatic nitriles for the synthesis of the corresponding amides. Reaction of 1-phenylethanol (**2**) with acetonitrile was taken as a model reaction to optimize the reaction conditions (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

After optimizing these conditions, the reactions were performed with various alcohols and other nitrile derivatives. The results of this study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Ritter reaction of various alcohols and nitriles catalyzed by amberlite IR-120 under microwave irradiation

Entry	Olefin (1)	Nitrile (2)	Product ^a (3)	Time (min)	Yields ^b (%)
1		CH ₃ CN		12	93
2		CH ₃ CN		10	92

Table-2 (contd.)

Table-2 (contd.)

3		13	90		
4		9	94		
5		11	89		
6		10	90		
7		12	88		
8		11	91		
9		12	90		
10		11	92		
11		14	88		
12		12	89		
13		13	91		
14		13	89		

15		12	93	
16		12	91	
17		13	92	
18		14	88	

(a) Isolated yields. (b) All the products are known, characterized by IR, NMR spectral analysis and compared with the authentic samples⁹⁻¹¹. (c) Melting points of compounds are consistent with reported values.

From mechanistic point of view, it is likely that proceeds via the protonation of alkenes (Scheme 3) and alcohols (Scheme 4) by influence [H⁺] the catalyst amberlite IR-120 [H⁺]. The resulting carbocation might be trapped by nitrile to give the nitrilium cation which subsequently reacts with water to furnish the desired amide.

The advantages or the characteristic aspects of the method described in this paper in comparison with other previously reported ones are the following : the yields of products were better than the previous reported yields and in addition, the catalyst amberlite IR-120 is inexpensive, has no moisture sensitivity, and no special measures are required for the reaction.

In summary, the present methodology shows that amberlite IR-120 is an efficient catalyst in the one-pot synthesis of α -arylethyl amides. The main advantages of this protocol being it is mild, environmentally benign and high yielding. Furthermore, this method is also expected to find application in organic synthesis due to the low cost of the reagent. It is believed that this method will be a useful addition to modern synthetic methodologies.

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

Experimental

All the reactions were carried out using a conventional (unmodified) microwave oven (LG, 230 V, ~50 Hz). Reactions were monitored on TLC by comparison with the samples prepared by known procedures. The infrared spectroscopy (IR) spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu 435-U-04 spectrophotometer (KBr pellets) and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ with Bruker 300 MHz high resolution NMR spectrometers. All melting points were determined on a Büchi 530 melting point apparatus and are reported uncorrected.

Microwave experiments were conducted using a CEM Discover monomode oven operating at 2450 MHz monitored by a PC computer, and temperature was maintained at a constant value by power modulation (0–300 W). Stirring was provided by an *in situ* magnetic stirrer. Reactions were performed in open glass vessels (capacity 10 ml). Reaction conditions : power 160 W; ramp time 1 min; hold time 3 min; stirring on.

Typical procedure for the synthesis of N-(1-phenylethyl)acetamide : A mixture of styrene (1 mmol), acetonitrile

(1 mmol), and amberlite IR-120 resin (0.16 g) was taken in the special open glass vessel. The mixture was thoroughly mixed, and the tube was then subjected to microwave irradiation according to the above protocol (see Table 1). After completion of the reaction as indicated by TLC, the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated NaHCO₃ solution and extracted with ethyl acetate (2 × 10 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Removal of the solvent followed by the purification on silica gel (Merck, 100–200 mesh, ethyl acetate-hexane, 0.5–9.5) gave the pure *N*-(1-phenylethyl)-acetamide.

Spectral data for selected compounds : compound **3** (Entry 1) : *N*-(1-phenylethyl)acetamide : white solid. m.p. 74–76 °C; IR (neat) : 3341, 1640 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ (ppm) 1.46 (3H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 1.96 (3H, s), 5.10 (1H, qt, *J* 6.8 Hz), 6.05 (1H, bs), 7.21–7.36 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.4 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ (ppm) 21.8, 23.5, 48.8, 126.3, 127.4, 128.7, 143.3, 169.3. MS : *m/z* Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃NO : 163.21; Found : 163 (M⁺).

General experimental procedure for synthesis of amides : A mixture of alcohol (1 mmol), nitrile (1 mmol), and amberlite IR-120 resin (0.16 g) was taken in the special open glass vessel. The mixture was thoroughly mixed, and the tube was then subjected to microwave irradiation according to the above protocol (see Table 2). After completion of the reaction as indicated by TLC, the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated NaHCO₃ solution and extracted with ethyl acetate (2 × 10 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Removal of the solvent followed by the purification on silica gel (Merck, 100–200 mesh, ethyl acetate–

hexane, 0.5–9.5) gave the pure amides.

The products thus obtained were characterized on the basis of their physical and spectral analysis and by direct comparison with literature data.

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